

Development of a multi-dimensional Key Performance Indicators' framework for the holistic performance assessment of Smart Grids

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Abstract:

Smart grids are considered to be innovative architectures that challenge the dominance of conventional distribution grids due to their advanced potential, based on the deployment of smart meters, communication grids, optimization strategies and increased share of Distributed Energy Resources (DER). In this context, dedicated platforms including a variety of software tools are required to support the Distribution System Operator (DSO) for the optimal management, design and planning of smart grids. This paper develops a framework for the holistic performance assessment of such platforms, including Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for technical, economic, environmental and social aspects of smart grids, but also overall platform KPIs in terms of their efficiency, accuracy and easiness to use. In this way, it does not only cover the performance assessment related to the operation and planning decisions of the smart grid, which is the usual approach, but it also covers the performance assessment of the platform engineering per se. The developed framework includes the possible data sources, calculation formulas and target values of the proposed KPIs, as well as their relation to the respective stakeholders, investigating different viewpoints (DSO, consumers, investors/prosumers, etc.) towards the formation of a holistic methodological framework.

Keywords:

Smart grid; Key performance indicators; Assessment; Framework.

1. Introduction

The transition towards a low-carbon energy sector is significantly transforming the architecture and operation of the electrical distribution grid. The common unidirectional, centralized, fossil fuel-based concept seems unable to efficiently cope with the new challenges [1]. Instead, smart grids constitute a promising solution, as their advanced metering infrastructures and digital communication grids allow for innovative, bidirectional, non-centralized and renewable-based architectures. Under these circumstances, Distribution System Operators (DSOs) face issues which did not exist before, such as complex grid operations, reliability issues, reverse power flows, etc. The aforementioned challenges may often be solved with the assistance of especially designed platforms that comprise tools which support the DSOs' transition towards an active system management approach [2]. Such platforms provide the DSOs with the capability of designing and operating the electrical grid optimally, taking into account the rapid deployment of Renewable Energy Sources (RES), energy dispatch issues and other growing concerns.

The assessment of platforms including tools towards the modernization of the electrical grid is a critical issue, before their wider adoption. In this sense, their performance regarding promised solutions can be evaluated, possible advantages or even drawbacks can be highlighted and comparison with other platforms/solutions can be accomplished. For this purpose, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are developed, which quantify the impact of the proposed solutions and compare it to respective target values. In the literature there is a variety of KPIs related to the performance evaluation of smart grids. For example, the authors of [3] propose a framework of technical, environmental, economic, social and legal KPIs for the development of smart grids on islands. The authors of [4] propose KPIs for the evaluation of a specific smart grid located in Malaga, Spain and divide them into two categories, i.e. main macro-objectives and secondary objectives, which comprise technical, environmental and economic KPIs. The authors of [5] evaluate the performance of a specific smart microgrid located in Italy which is based mostly on Photovoltaic (PV) systems, using predominantly technical KPIs. Additionally, in [6], technical and environmental KPIs are presented for the evaluation of a smart grid located in a university in Romania along with results derived from the monitoring systems. However, the aforementioned studies concern specific cases, meaning that their KPIs' framework is designed especially for

them and cannot be generalized easily or would not cover several aspects of other cases. Following a more generalized approach, in [7], the performance and sustainability potential of smart cities including smart grids is assessed, highlighting mostly their technical, environmental and economic features. Furthermore, in [8–10], technical and environmental KPIs that focus on the assessment of smart grids in terms of reliability, power quality and sustainability are extensively analyzed. Also, the authors of [11] present a set of KPIs related to demand-response management strategies for smart grids with special attention to consumption, uncertainties and financial benefits and the authors of [12] propose KPIs for the assessment of smart grids with special focus on social aspects and active consumers. Yet, the studies analyzed above only focus on the resulting grid improvement, without evaluating the platform itself (which is responsible for the observed improvement) and its usability.

The purpose of this paper is to present a framework of KPIs for the holistic performance assessment of smart grids, including their technical, environmental, economic and social aspects, but also the performance specifications/capabilities of the platforms that render their management possible in an efficient manner, as presented in Figure 1. Thus, it expands the purpose of the existing literature. The developed framework analyzes the relation of the stakeholders, i.e., system operators (DSOs, etc.), consumers, investors/aggregators/prosumers, to the smart grid's management and develops detailed instructions in order to attain the values of the proposed KPIs.

Figure 1. Main aspects of smart grids.

2. Categories of KPIs and their relation to stakeholders

The main categories of KPIs can be divided into technical, environmental, economic, social and platform engineering, whereas the stakeholders may be divided into system operators, consumers and investors/aggregators/prosumers, as presented in Table 1. The technical KPIs concern mostly the system operators, which typically include the DSOs and in some cases the Transmission System Operator (TSO), etc., as their primary concern is the reliability, power quality and efficiency of the smart grid's operation [3]. The environmental KPIs concern all stakeholders as the mitigation of CO₂ emissions is a target of the system operators but also a key-factor for the improvement of life quality of the consumers and the basis of many energy-related investments (either by companies or prosumers) that focus on RES, ranging from rooftop PV panels up to Wind Farms (WF). The economic KPIs are related to the system operators through the operation, maintenance and expansion of the smart grid. They are also associated with the energy cost that is reflected on the bills of the consumers. Furthermore, they are related to the profits of investments, such as RES and storage systems, but also the profits of aggregators, e.g. aggregators of electric vehicles with Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) capability, and to the profits of the prosumers, e.g. selling energy from home-installed PV panels to the system operator. The social KPIs are mostly about the consumers, as they may either adopt or reprove various

smart grid policies, from demand-response strategies up to RES applications (initiatives related to either individual or large scale installations) [13]. Last, but not least, the platform engineering itself is associated to all stakeholders, as the accuracy of the platform's tools is directly linked to the smart grid's management but it mostly affects the system operators, which require a user-friendly, adaptable and usable platform.

Table 1. Categories of KPIs and stakeholders ([3, 12]).

KPI categories	System operators		
Technical	Efficient power supply, low losses, high reliability and power quality.	Seamless, safe operation, with sufficient power quality, without black-outs.	Development and implementation of RES that do not affect the grid's performance in a negative way (flicker, congestion, etc.).
Environmental	Operation with low CO ₂ emissions. Priority to RES production harvesting.	Life quality, in terms of "clean" energy, reduction of pollution from the energy sector, etc.	RES-based solutions, with efficient performance and low energy requirements and CO ₂ emissions during the manufacturing process.
Economic	Low cost for operation, maintenance and expansion of the smart grid.	Low cost of electricity bills, regarding both energy prices and fixed cost.	High profit of investment, maximum net present value (NPV), energy sold at profitable prices.
Social	Proposition and acceptance of strategies that activate the consumers (demand-response, time-of-use tariffs, etc.).	Sustainable development with special attention to energy sufficiency, cost policies and landscape deterioration.	Engagement in socially accepted investments, grid development actions with the assent of the local community.
Platform engineering	User-friendly design with low requirements and high accuracy.	Accurate solutions, avoiding insufficient operation or extra cost of energy supply due to deviations from actual values or errors.	Adaptability regarding various initiatives, efficient incorporation in the energy management system.

3. Development of the KPIs framework

The purpose of this Section is to present the KPIs of each category and provide specifications as well as their relation to the smart grid's operation or investment decisions, including the main stakeholders. The values of the KPIs can either be compared to a benchmark provided by this framework or to the results of another platform's tool.

3.1. Technical KPIs

The technical KPIs, which are presented in Table 2, are related to the smart grid's performance. Their values can be calculated using measurements from the sensors and metering devices of the smart grid and are usually calculated on yearly basis. The first three KPIs are used for the evaluation of the smart grid's reliability. The respective calculation formulas for: i) System Average Interruption Frequency Index (SAIFI), ii) System Average Interruption Duration Index (SAIDI) and iii) Customer Average Interruption Duration Index (CAIDI), are presented in Eqs. (1-3). Indicatively, acceptable values are 1.10 interruptions per customer for SAIFI [14], 15 minutes up to 1.5 hour for SAIDI [15] and 1.36 hours for CAIDI [16]. The fourth and fifth technical KPIs are related to losses. Technical losses comprise distribution line losses (affected by ambient temperature and manufacturing material), transformer losses, etc. On the other hand, non-technical losses are the result of fraud. However, it is difficult to determine the cause of losses in a smart grid (technical or non-technical) and specialized tools or even on-the-spot inspection may be required. In case of technical losses, their reduction can be achieved through the installation of local supply units, preferably RES and storage systems, which increase the self-consumption of the smart grid with minimum environmental impact. In fact, since the EU goal for 2030 is to have RES share equal to 40%, a good value for technical losses would be the one corresponding

to having 40% distributed, local RES production in the smart grid [17]. The sixth technical KPI, i.e. flicker [18], is related to power quality and needs to be taken into account especially when it comes to investments and installations of large RES plants (e.g., WFs). It can be calculated for short terms, P_{st} , obtained for ten-minute periods using Eq. (4), but also for long terms, P_{lt} , obtained for two-hour periods using Eq. (5). It is noted that the term t_f of Eq. (4) is the flicker severity caused by voltage change. Flicker can be estimated during the planning stage of an investment and can also be measured by special flickermeters if the plant is already installed. In literature, the maximum allowable value for P_{st} is 0.9 and the maximum allowable value for P_{lt} is 0.7 [18]. The seventh technical KPI denotes voltage deviation (drop or rise from the nominal value), which undermines the smart grid's power quality especially if it exceeds 0.05 p.u. [19]. Finally, the power quality KPIs are completed by taking into account harmonic distortion, which can be reduced with the use of appropriate filters. The Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) is calculated by Eq. (6), where $V_{n RMS}$ is the RMS voltage of the n-th harmonic and $V_{1 RMS}$ is the RMS value of the fundamental voltage, while a good target value is considered to be maximum equal to 5% [20].

Table 2. Technical KPIs ([14]-[20]).

SN	Name	Relevance	Stakeholders	Unit	Target/Usual values
1	SAIFI	Operation		-, Eq. (1)	1.10 interruptions per customer [14]
2	SAIDI	Operation		h, Eq. (2)	15 m – 1.5 h [15]
3	CAIDI	Operation		h, Eq. (3)	1.36 h [16]
4	Technical losses	Oper. & Invest.		kWh	At least equal to the value corresponding to having 40% RES share [17]
5	Non-technical losses	Operation		kWh	Ideally 0
6	Flicker	Oper. & Invest.		-, Eq. (4,5)	0.9 short term, 0.7 long term [18]
7	Voltage deviation	Oper. & Invest.		p.u.	±0.05 p.u. [19]
8	Harmonic distortion	Oper. & Invest.		%, Eq. (6)	5% [20]

$$SAIFI = \frac{\text{Total number of customer interruptions}}{\text{Total number of customers served}} \quad (1)$$

$$SAIDI = \frac{\text{Sum of all customer interruption durations}}{\text{Total number of customers served}} \quad (2)$$

$$CAIDI = \frac{\text{Sum of all customer interruption durations}}{\text{Total number of customer interruptions}} \quad (3)$$

$$P_{st} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{\sum t_f}{10}} \quad (4)$$

$$P_{lt} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{\sum_{j=1}^{12} P_{st j}^3}{12}} \quad (5)$$

$$THD = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{n=2} V_n^2_{RMS}}}{V_1_{RMS}} \quad (6)$$

3.2. Environmental KPIs

The environmental KPIs are presented in Table 3. Their values can be calculated using specifications given by the manufacturers of various technologies/installations (PV parks, storage systems, etc.) and measurements from the smart sensors. The first environmental KPI, i.e. the Net Energy Ratio (NER), is related to new investments, usually to large RES installations and Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS), but may also be applied to conventional Distributed Energy Resources (DER), such as diesel generators, etc. The purpose of NER is to ensure that the proposed investment shall supply the grid with more energy by the end of its lifetime than the energy required for its manufacturing and erection, as presented in Eq. (7). Therefore, the target value needs to be at least equal to 1, otherwise it is not worth proceeding with the proposed investment. Of course, when there are two or more proposed investments, the one with the highest NER is the most preferable. The direct CO₂ emissions constitute a KPI that is related to both operation and investments. Regarding the smart grid's operation, direct CO₂ emissions can be monitored through the metering system and the target of the European Union (EU) is to achieve 55% reduction of CO₂ and other greenhouse gas emissions by 2030 compared to 1990 levels, which is similar to aiming for 55% reduction of emissions compared to having no DER, especially RES, in the smart grid [17]. The reduction of direct CO₂ emissions can be achieved through the implementation of RES, which is the reason for selecting them over fuel-based DER, e.g., diesel generators, when it comes to proposals for the grid's expansion (investments). Of course, the smart grid operator needs to ensure that the RES shall operate seamlessly, without curtailment due to congestion issues or unbalances.

Table 3. Environmental KPIs ([17]).

SN	Name	Relevance	Stakeholders	Unit	Target/Usual values
1	NER	Investment		-, Eq. (7)	>1, as high as possible
2	Direct CO ₂ emissions	Oper. & Invest.		tons of CO ₂	55% reduction [17]
3	RES curtailment	Operation		kWh	Ideally 0

$$NER = \frac{\text{Lifetime energy supply}}{\text{Total energy invested}} \quad (7)$$

3.3. Economic KPIs

The economic KPIs are presented in Table 4 and constitute a category upon which most of the planning/investment decisions are made. The first two economic KPIs concern the system operator. More specifically, the Operational Expenditure (OPEX) denotes the cost for the usual line of business, focusing on the cost of the utilized energy mix, which is still predominantly based on natural gas or coal (with severely high cost this year, close to 200 €/MWh [21], due to the current global energy crisis). On the other hand, the Capital Expenditure (CAPEX) is related to the grid's extension, investments, etc. For example, it is estimated that the installation cost of a typical medium voltage overhead line is equal to 160,000 €/km, while the installation cost of the same sort of line underground is equal to 840,000 €/km [22]. Also, the installation cost of PV systems and WFs is estimated to be close to 1,000,000 €/MW [23]. When it comes to investments, the decision can be made upon the NPV [24], presented in Eq. (8), where CF_i is the cash flow of the i -th year, N is the project lifetime in years and k is the annual discount rate. Indicatively, the project lifetime of PV parks is estimated to be equal to 20-25 years. The NPV needs to be positive. In case of more than one proposed investments, the one with the highest NPV is the most preferable. Furthermore, the payback time of the investment is considered to be a significant indicator, calculated accurately using Eq. (8) as the time when NPV becomes equal to zero, or much simpler by (9). This indicator practically refers to the amount of time that is required to recover the cost of an investment. For example, a PV installation is considered successful when it has payback time close to 8 years, depending on the location (lower payback times are expected in areas close to the equator) [25]. Higher payback time is expected for WFs, depending on their size, in most cases exceeding 10 years [26]. In order to estimate the profitability of potential investments, a vastly utilized metric is the Internal Rate of Return (IRR), i.e. the annual rate of growth that an investment is expected to generate. IRR is calculated using Eq. (8) and is equal to the discount rate that makes the NPV equal to zero. The expected values have a wide

range as they are related to the location, the energy policies and the size of the plant. Indicatively, most renewables have IRR ranging from 7% to 20% [27–30]. Additionally, regarding the consumers, the target for the cost (which includes both operation and investment expenses) is to be minimized. Usual values range from 0.1-0.25 €/kWh [31] and the overall value is related to each consumer's category and consumption band.

Table 4. Economic KPIs ([24]-[32]).

SN	Name	Relevance	Stakeholders	Unit	Target/Usual values
1	OPEX	Operation		€	Depending on the fuel mix and the dramatically mutable fuel prices
2	CAPEX	Investment		€	Depending on the equipment type
3	NPV	Investment		€, Eq. (8)	>0, as high as possible [24]
4	Payback time	Investment		years, Eq. (9)	8 years for typical PV system [25]
5	IRR	Investment		%	7%-20% [27–30]
6	Cost per consumer	Oper. & Invest.		€	0.10-0.25 €/kWh [31]

$$NPV = \sum_{i=0}^N \frac{CF_i}{(1+k)^i} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Simple payback time} = \frac{\text{Investment}}{\text{Annual cash flow}} \quad (9)$$

3.4. Social KPIs

Regarding the social aspect of a smart grid's management, it is critical to take into account the consumers' point of view, following the KPIs of Table 5. The adoption or acceptance of actions related to the grid's operation or new investments (demand-response strategy, installation of WFs in public spaces, massive use of fuel-based energy, etc.), as well as the good evaluation of price policies (cost of electric bills) and fault repair (e.g., in case of an emergency) are critical matters [3, 12]. The values of these KPIs can be obtained through psychometric scales, such as Likert scale, in respective questionnaires. For a range from 1 to 5 (where 5 is the most satisfying outcome), the target value for the average consumer may be set equal to at least 3 (neutral response).

Table 5. Social KPIs ([3, 12]).

SN	Name	Relevance	Stakeholders	Unit	Target/Usual values
1	Adoption/acceptance of proposed strategies	Oper. & Invest.		-	≥3 (for maximum equal to 5)
2	Evaluation of cost of electricity bills	Operation		-	≥3 (for maximum equal to 5)
3	Evaluation of fault repair	Operation		-	≥3 (for maximum equal to 5)

3.5. Platform engineering KPIs

The final category examined is the platform engineering KPIs, displayed in Table 6. Targeting and optimizing the KPIs in this category can have an overall positive impact on all the categories previously presented. The tool accuracy refers to the accuracy of the results that the algorithms used in the platform produce, when evaluated using already validated data. The error rate is the percentage between failed and total requests made on the platform and is given by Eq. (10). A usual target for this KPI is 5% [33]. Average Central

Processing Unit (CPU) usage and average memory usage are given by Eq. (11) and Eq. (12) respectively, and address the resources needed per request made on the platform. These values can vary depending on the implemented algorithms and the need they serve. For instance, a typical but quite efficient power flow algorithm, like the one proposed in [34], which serves the need of detailed grid modelling, has an average CPU usage of 1.63 s/request and an average memory usage of 4.21 MB/request when applied on grids containing an average of 460 nodes. It should be noted that the aforementioned KPIs can be easily recorded by the platform itself. Last but not least, the user interface friendliness and user satisfaction can determine the usability of the platform and may be obtained through psychometric scales, e.g. Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5, by the system operators.

Table 6. Platform engineering KPIs ([33, 34]).

SN	Name	Relevance	Stakeholders	Unit	Target/Usual values
1	Tool accuracy	Operation		%	Depends on the algorithm
2	Error rate	Usability		%, Eq. (10)	5% [33]
3	Average CPU usage	Platform resources		s/request, Eq. (11)	1.63 s/request for grids averaging 460 nodes [34]
4	Average memory usage	Platform resources		MB/request, Eq. (12)	4.21 MB/request for grids averaging 460 nodes [34]
5	User interface friendliness	Usability		-	≥3 (for maximum equal to 5)
6	User satisfaction	Usability		-	≥3 (for maximum equal to 5)

$$Error\ rate = \frac{\sum failed\ requests}{\sum total\ requests} * 100\% \quad (10)$$

$$Average\ CPU\ usage = \frac{\sum uptime\ for\ every\ request}{\sum total\ requests} \quad (11)$$

$$Average\ memory\ usage = \frac{\sum memory\ required\ for\ every\ request}{\sum total\ requests} \quad (12)$$

4. Discussion

Overall, there is a variety of KPIs which a platform managing a smart grid may be evaluated upon. Many of them may accord with each other, however there may also be contradictions. For example, the deployment of large RES plants can mitigate the technical losses, lower the direct CO₂ emissions and also have a high NPV for the investors, but there are cases where it might also degrade the power quality KPIs or even face objections by the community [13]. Another contemporary example is the establishment of Electric Vehicle Aggregators (EVA), which not only charge the vehicles, but may also support V2G mode in order to profit from selling energy to the smart grid [35]. This solution lowers the technical losses, can have high NPV and normally reduces the direct CO₂ emissions (especially if the charging stations are equipped with PV panels), but may have a negative effect in the DSO's OPEX or even contradict the profits of other aggregators. Moreover, solutions that include many DER and rely heavily on forecasts and uncertain consumer behavior may improve a range of KPIs, especially related to efficiency, power quality, satisfactory costs and profits for all parties, but on the other hand they may frequently lead to reduced tool accuracy or even increased error rates from the aspect of platform engineering [36]. Taking all the aforementioned examples into account, it is evident that for each operation mode or grid expansion, all relevant KPIs should be evaluated in order for such issues to be tackled effectively. It is in the system operator's discretion to weigh the impact of each KPI in order to make the optimal decisions.

Although there are many ways to perform efficient smart grid management, it appears that usually the generally accepted and beneficial solutions rely on strategies that include the activation of the consumers. This can be

achieved in a number of ways. Perhaps one of the most common solutions with both easy implementation and wide public acceptance is the application of time-of-use tariffs [37]. In this way, part of the load time-series is shifted by the consumers themselves, resulting to the reduction of their electricity bills, the reduction of voltage deviations and the avoidance of congestion in the distribution grid that might even lead to interruption of power supply, especially during extremely warm or cold periods of the year. Yet, this approach is quite simple and is better to be implemented along with more advanced, RES-based strategies, in order to have a more improved outcome. In this sense, there are many cases where the activation of the consumers is proposed to be achieved through the transition towards autonomous buildings or districts, which essentially turns the consumers into prosumers [38]. Over the past few years, many consumers have installed PV panels on the rooftops of their residences and workplaces, sometimes coupled with storage systems aiming at autonomy enhancement. At this point it should be noted that PV panels constitute a RES with remarkably easy deployment in urban areas, as they have fewer space and weight concerns than most of their alternatives. Such initiatives increase the efficiency and power quality of the distribution grid, reduce its energy footprint, result in cost savings, are -in general- accepted by the public and can be combined with other components under various policies.

To sum up, smart grids offer a variety of possibilities for the optimization of the energy dispatch as well as the decisions related to grid planning/expansion, based on the smart sensors, advanced communication networks and innovative algorithms that they deploy [39]. The results can be evaluated upon technical, environmental, economic, social and also platform engineering criteria, from various viewpoints, i.e. those of system operators, consumers and investors, aggregators or prosumers. Even though there is no solution that satisfies simultaneously and equally all of the stakeholders, by taking the proposed KPIs into account a holistic, overall improved solution can be approached.

5. Conclusions

This paper presents a multi-dimensional framework of KPIs for the holistic performance assessment of smart grids, the management of which is accomplished through advanced, innovative algorithms implemented in dedicated control platforms. The proposed framework is general, thus applicable to any smart grid, and it covers all main aspects, including technical, environmental, economic, social and platform engineering KPIs, in contrast to existing case-specific frameworks, which are developed according to certain, explicit requirements, or frameworks including less aspects, which usually omit the assessment of the platform's design or do not focus on social parameters. For each KPI, specifications are provided, including the processes it addresses, i.e. operation, investment, usability, etc., the stakeholders that it involves, as well as the details regarding its calculation and target/usual values, in order to facilitate the assessment of the smart grid's performance.

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Nomenclature

Acronyms

BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
CAIDI	Customer Average Interruption Duration Index
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EU	European Union
EVA	Electric Vehicle Aggregator
IRR	Internal Rate of Return
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NER	Net Energy Ratio
NPV	Net Present Value
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
PV	Photovoltaic
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SAIDI	System Average Interruption Duration Index
SAIFI	System Average Interruption Frequency Index
SN	Serial Number
THD	Total Harmonic Distortion

TSO	Transmission System Operator
V2G	Vehicle-to-Grid
WF	Wind Farm

Symbols

CF	Cash flow (€)
k	Annual discount rate (%)
P_{st}	Short-term flicker (-)
P_{lt}	Long-term flicker (-)
t_f	Flicker severity, caused by voltage change (-)
V	Voltage (V)

Subscripts and superscripts

i	Index of the year of the investment
j	Index of measurement/sample
n	Index of the order of the harmonic voltage
N	Lifetime of investment
RMS	Root Mean Square

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